

ASSESSING THE IMPACTS OF NATIONAL POLICIES ON INDONESIAN AUTONOMOUS UNIVERSITIES' RESEARCH PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aimed to examine the potential impact of policies granting Indonesian top universities with special autonomy status called as Legal Entity State University, or *Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum* (PTN-BH), on their research performance. This study involved an analysis of eight national policy documents related to PTN-BH or autonomous universities, which were retrieved from a trusted government regulation database webpage. All the data were collected from existing documents, making this research a document study, with data interpretation conducted through content analysis. The findings reveal that the regulations on the requirements and procedures for PTN-BH status, as well as the policy on the funding types and schemes, have contributed to the research performance disparities between universities that were granted PTN-BH status at different points in time. The updated regulations have lowered and simplified the requirements and procedures for obtaining PTN-BH status, allowing universities with lower initial performance to apply. Universities' ability to comply with the funding policy of self-generating income, matching-fund, and performance-based funding system also influence the universities' budgeting allocation, including for research activity. Lastly, the regulation on giving autonomy to universities in deciding their top managerial structure leading to various designations in assigning a vice-rector to manage the research affairs is also a significant factor in the university's research performance.

KEYWORDS:

higher education policy, PTN-BH, autonomous university, university research outcomes, content analysis

INTRODUCTION

In the Indonesian higher education (HE) system and governance, the central government's obligation is explained in an official document titled Government Regulation No. 4 Year 2014. This regulation states that the government's primary responsibility in the HE system and governance is to assure the quality and autonomy of Indonesian higher education institutions (HEIs) to serve citizens who are seeking a quality HE degree. In addition to fulfilling the country's interests and aiding domestic stakeholders including students, parents, society, and business companies, the Indonesian government has been continuously making efforts to meet the globalization demands. Therefore, the government has implemented policies focusing on managing and supporting public universities to give them the capabilities and resources to compete globally and earn global or international recognition and reputation as world class universities. Indonesia, like other countries, especially those in Asia, has been following the trend of providing special aid to selected top universities enacted under national projects or policies (Balatsky & Ekimova, 2020; Han et al., 2018; Hartley & Jarvis, 2021; King et al., 2011; Matveeva et al., 2021; Mok et al., 2020; Sugimura, 2016). Within the national project context, global reputation usually refers to a university securing a certain position in one or more international university rankings, for example, Academic Ranking of World

Universities (ARWU), Times Higher Education World University Ranking (THE WUR), and QS World University Ranking (QS).

Withing the context of Indonesian higher education, becoming a world class university is defined by inclusion in one or more world university ranking systems. Considering that most university rankings indicators give more weighting on research performance ranging between one-third to two-thirds of the final score (Akbash et al. (2021), this aspect is given more attention by both government and universities in pursuing the world class university status and followed by significant efforts to improve Indonesian university research performance and outcomes. In trying to attain the global competitiveness of Indonesian HEIs, the Indonesian government formulated Government Regulation No. 61 in 1999 concerning establishing Indonesian HEIs' autonomy to improve their potential and strategic strength to compete globally. This regulation directed toward identification of public universities with sufficient management capabilities to attain greater autonomy, responsibility, and independence. Therefore, the government considers the possibility of selectively upgrading the managerial status and autonomy of qualified public universities into a Legal Entity State University or, in the Indonesian language, *Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum* (PTN-BH). Although the policy on PTN-BH was initiated in 1999, a clearer official guideline on PTN-BH establishment was issued in 2012 through Indonesian National Decree No. 12 Year 2012 concerning Higher Education. The Decree states that special autonomy can be selectively granted to public universities based on a performance evaluation conducted by the Minister of Education and Culture. Later in 2013, the government considered seven public universities as having fulfilled the requirement to be granted PTN-BH status. However, only four public universities completed the procedures and requirements to upgrade to the new status, leaving three others to accomplish this later in 2014, along with four additional public universities. Despite the government's enthusiasm for creating PTN-BHs, their number has remained stagnant for seven years (2013–2020), with only 11 out of 122 public universities reaching this status (Ministry of Education and Culture Republic Indonesia, 2020). By the end of 2020, the PTN-BH status was awarded to only one more public university, and around mid-2021, five more public universities were granted this status, totaling 17 PTN-BHs by the end of 2021. Considering the nature of PTN-BH university governance, these 17 universities are also considered as Indonesian top public universities to date.

In general, the Indonesian national policy of PTN-BH has successfully had 13 out of the 17 PTN-BHs be enlisted among the 678 HEIs in QS Asia University Rankings 2022. However, despite the expectation of witnessing similar major improvements in all PTN-BHs, discrepancies in the universities' performance are observable. The data obtained from Elsevier's *SciVal* database in 2022 exposes considerable disparities in research performance among three Indonesian PTN-BH groups categorized by their respective appointment dates. The first group consists of four universities that were entitled PTN-BH status in 2013, the second group are seven universities that were granted the status in 2014, and the third group covers six universities earning the status in 2020 and 2021. The overall research performance of the first group shows 52,025 scholarly outputs from 42,806 authors who received 170,651 citations, or 3.3 citations per publication. The second group achieved 48,595 outputs by 41,643 authors with 122,303 citations or 2.5 per publication. The third group reached 19,095 scholarly outputs written by 17,408 authors who gained 49,643 citations, or 2.6 citations per publication. The data showing research performance divide among the PTN-BH universities implies that despite identical entitlement and assistance granted through national policy, there might be impacts from changes made in the policies regulating PTN-BH within a 20 year-time span. Thus, this study was conducted to examine how national policies on PTN-BH have impacted the PT-NBH universities' research performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a qualitative study employing document analysis on one of the higher education system policies in Indonesia, specifically focusing on the establishment of PTN-BH. The data were collected from various national policy documents in the form of government regulations, national laws, ministerial regulation, and ministerial decrees. A total of eight national policy documents were collected from a trustworthy source, accessible at <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/>. The list of the documents is as follows:

1. *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 61 Tahun 1999 Tentang Penetapan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Sebagai Badan Hukum*. [Indonesian Government Regulation Number 16 Year 1999 concerning the Establishment of PTN-BH].
2. *Undang-undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 12 Tahun 2012 Tentang Pendidikan Tinggi*. [The National Decree Number 12 Year 2012 concerning Higher Education].
3. *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 58 Tahun 2013 Tentang Bentuk Dan Mekanisme Pendanaan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum*. [Indonesian Government Regulation No. 58 Year 2013 concerning Types and Mechanism of Funding for PTN-BH].
4. *Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 88 Tahun 2014 Tentang Perubahan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Menjadi Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum*. [Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) Regulation No. 88 Year 2014 concerning the Conversion of Public University into PTN-BH].
5. *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 26 Tahun 2015 Tentang Bentuk Dan Mekanisme Pendanaan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum*. [Indonesian Government Regulation No. 26 Year 2015 concerning Types and Mechanism of Funding for PTN-BH].
6. *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 8 Tahun 2020 Tentang Perubahan Atas Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 26 Tahun 2015 Tentang Bentuk dan Mekanisme Pendanaan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum*. [Indonesian Government Regulation No. 8 Year 2020 concerning Amendment of Republic of Indonesian Government Regulation No. 26 Year 2015].
7. *Keputusan Direktur Jenderal Pendidikan Tinggi, Riset, Dan Teknologi Kementerian Pendidikan, Kebudayaan, Riset, Dan Teknologi Republik Indonesia Nomor H4/E/Kpt/2021 Tentang Pedoman Pendanaan Berbasis Capaian Indikator Kinerja Utama Perguruan Tinggi Negeri di Lingkungan Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Tinggi, Riset, dan Teknologi*. [The Decree of the Director General of Higher Education, Research, and Technology No.114/E/KPT/2021 concerning The Guidelines of Main-Performance-Indicator-Achievement-based-Funding for public universities under the Directorate General of Higher Education, Research, and Technology's supervision].
8. *Keputusan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 3/M/2021 tentang Indikator Kinerja Utama Perguruan Tinggi Negeri dan Lembaga Layanan Pendidikan Tinggi di Kemeterian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*. [The Decree of Minister of Education and Culture No. 3/M/2021 concerning Main Performance Indicators of Public University and Higher Education Institutions under the Ministry of Education and Culture's supervision].

Additionally, to supplement the national policy documents, universities' top management organizational structures were downloaded from Indonesian 17 PTN-BH universities' official websites. These universities were appointed as PTN-BH from the year 2013 up to 2021. For anonymity and ease of reference, these universities were assigned codes from U1 to U17 in sequential order based on their respective appointment dates as PTN-BH institutions. The universities were grouped into three batches based on the order of the appointment dates and coded as follows:

- a. The first batch: The four universities granted PTN-BH status in 2013 are coded as U1, U2, U3, and U4.
- b. The second batch: The seven universities granted PTN-BH status in 2014 are coded as U1, U2, U3, U4, U5, U6, and U7.
- c. The third batch: The six universities granted PTN-BH status in 2020 and 2021 are coded as U1, U2, U3, U4, U5, and U6.

In addition to the year of appointment, the reason behind the grouping into three batches is based on the differences in the government regulation used as the reference for the appointment in the three different periods, that is, the National Decree Number 12 the Year 2012 concerning HE for the first batch, the Indonesian Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) Regulation No. 88 the Year 2014 for the second batch, and the Indonesian MoEC Regulation No. 4 the Year 2020 for the third batch. Regarding the focus of the current research, that is, the disparities in research performance and potential affecting factors contributed by national and institutional policies, Table 1 illustrates the universities' grouping and research performance differences.

Table 1. List of the 17 PTN-BH Universities and Their Scholarly Outputs in 2022

Grouping	University Codes	Total of Scholarly Outputs
1 st batch	U1	12,800
	U2	7,856
	U3	13,428
	U4	21,285
2 nd batch	U5	4,302
	U6	7,045
	U7	9,723
	U8	6,628
	U9	7,177
	U10	7,475
	U11	8,004
3 rd batch	U12	7,045
	U13	3,049
	U14	7,485
	U15	4,508
	U16	1,414
	U17	3,841

Source: The scholarly output data was collected from Scival.com (2022).

Then, a content analysis was performed by thoroughly reading the whole documents while identifying and categorizing themes related to aspects that potentially influence the variations in research performance among these universities. To maintain the trustworthiness of the analysis, the research team conducted peer-review, evaluating each other's work and engaging in discussions to achieve a consensus on the findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Within the national policy documents, two prominent aspects were found to be impactful: (1) the regulation changes on the requirements, accreditation status, and procedures to be granted PTN-BH status, and (2) the regulation on funding types and schemes. Meanwhile, the organizational structure of top management leadership of each university was also identified

to be impactful.

Impact of Changes on Requirements and Procedures Regulated in the National Policies of PTN-BH

The disparities found among the PTN-BHs within the same batches could have resulted from the changes in government policies related to the requirements the universities must meet to be granted PTN-BH status. National policy regulating the requirements and procedures for public universities seeking PTN-BH status has been updated at least three times. The requirements are stated in (a) Indonesian Government Regulation No. 16 Year 1999 concerning the Establishment of PTN-BH and National Decree No. 12 Year 2012 concerning HE; (b) Indonesian MoEC Regulation No. 88 Year 2014 concerning the Conversion of Public University into PTN-BH; and (c) Indonesian MoEC Regulation No. 4 Year 2020 concerning the Amendment of MoEC Regulation No. 88 Year 2014. The changes in the requirements, accreditation status, and procedures over the three different regulation periods are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The Changes in Requirements and Procedures for Universities to be Appointed as PTN-BH

No.	Themes	1999 & 2012 Regulation	2014 Regulation	2020 Regulation
1.	Requirements	The university must have proven to have abilities in: a. conducting efficient and high-quality HE, b. meeting the minimum standard of financial adequacy, and c. managing HEIs based on economics and accountability principles.	The university must have proven to have the ability in: a. conducting three high-quality pillars (tri dharma) of HE, b. managing the university organization based on good governance principles, c. meeting the minimum standard of financial adequacy, d. taking on social responsibilities, e. taking a role in economic development.	The university must have proven to have abilities in: a. conducting three high-quality pillars (tri dharma) of HE, b. managing the university organization based on good governance principles, c. meeting the minimum standard of financial adequacy, d. taking on social responsibilities, e. taking a role in economic development.
2.	Accreditation status	Not regulated	The university and at least 80% of its study programs must obtain the highest national accreditation status.	The university and at least 60% of its study programs must obtain the highest national accreditation status.
3.	Procedure	Top-down procedure: Autonomy status is granted selectively based on the performance	The top-down procedure with more details explained: a. The initiative to upgrade a public	Either top-down or bottom-up a. The initiative to upgrade a public university's status

<p>evaluation conducted by the authoritative minister, that is, the Minister of Education and Culture (MoEC).</p>	<p>university into a PTN-BH comes from the minister.</p> <p>b. The initiative is then informed of the given university.</p> <p>c. If the university agrees with the initiation, the university leader prepares and submits a proposal for status upgrading to a PTN-BH.</p> <p>d. The minister appoints an independent team of at least five experts to evaluate the university's performance.</p>	<p>into PTN-BH may come from either the minister or the university.</p> <p>b. The university leaders prepare and submit a proposal document.</p> <p>c. The remaining procedures are the same as the 2014 regulation.</p>
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Within the first period of regulation, the requirements for a public university to obtain PTN-BH status were fewer, and the requirement for institutional and study program accreditation status was not determined. However, three universities belonging to the first group—U4, U3, and U1—showed exemplary performance among all PTN-BHs. These three universities belonged to those that were carefully evaluated and selected by the government (MoEC) based on their initial performance, potential, and readiness to advance with the newly granted autonomy status.

Referring to Table 1, the data also indicate that universities in the second and third groups granted PTN-BH status saw wide gaps in scholarly outputs compared to the universities that fall under the first batch group. The lowering of the requirements on accreditation status for both the institutions and study programs accompanies the changes in national policy. In the 2014 regulation, a university had to have 80% of its study programs accredited with the highest score of A to be eligible to apply for PTN-BH status. However, in 2020, the requirement for the number of study programs accredited as A had been reduced to only 60%.

Finally, as seen in Table 2, although in the 1999 and 2012 regulations and the 2014 regulation, the initiative to upgrade a public university's status into PTN-BH originates from the MoEC, based on the 2020 regulation, the initiative may come from either the minister or university. In accordance with the latest regulation, a public university has the capacity to draft a proposal based on its self-evaluation to convince the government of the autonomy status upgrading assessment.

Impact of Funding Types and Schemes Regulation for PTN-BH Universities

Funding and finance management are among the most prominent aspects for an organization, including HEIs, to run and perform well. The Government of Indonesia has dynamically considered the funding of and budgeting for PTN-BHs by provisioning four regulations on the type and mechanism of funding through four key regulations: (a) Indonesian Government Regulation No. 58 Year 2013 concerning Types and Mechanism of Funding for PTN-BH; (b) Indonesian Government Regulation No. 26 Year 2015 concerning Types and Mechanism of Funding for PTN-BH; (c) Indonesian Government Regulation No. 8 Year 2020, an amendment

to the Republic of Indonesian Government Regulation No. 26 Year 2015; and (d) the Decree of the Director General of Higher Education, Research, and Technology (DGHERT) No.114/E/KPT/2021 concerning the Guidelines of Performance-Based Funding System for Public Universities in Indonesia.

Although significant differences are identified when comparing the 2013 regulation to the 2015 regulation, the 2015 and 2020 regulations are found to carry similar guidelines in terms of funding type and mechanism. The 2020 version includes the acknowledgement of the Ministry of Religion Affairs as the authority regulating PTN-BH of Islamic universities and the MoEC as the authoritative supervisor of public universities. Two main differences in the 2013 regulation compared with the 2015/2020 ones are the allowed additional funding sources and types of budgeting allotment. The documents show that starting from 2015, PTN-BHs are allowed to have two additional funding sources from regional revenue and expenditure budgets and loans, in addition to the previously approved additional funding sources generated from public or community, tuition, and fees, endowment funds, university's enterprises or businesses, cooperation in higher education *Tri-dharma* (education, research, and community service), state assets handed over to PTN-BHs by central or local government, and any other legitimate sources. Although, according to both 2013 and 2015/2020 regulations, PTN-BHs are entitled to State University Operational Assistance (*Bantuan Operasional Perguruan Tinggi Negeri* abbreviated as BOPTN) and PTN-BH Funding Assistance (*Bantuan Pendanaan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Badan Hukum* abbreviated as BPPTN-BH), how the PTN-BHs should allocate the BPPTN-BH funding was not yet regulated in the 2013 regulation. Later, 2015/2020 regulations state that funding must be allocated to five sectors: operating costs, faculty member/lecturer fees, administration personnel fees, investment costs, and development costs.

In 2021, the government adjusted the funding type and mechanism for PTN-BH by issuing the Decree of the DGHERT No.114/E/KPT/2021. The policy was enacted to regulate the funding schemes for public universities based on their achievement of the targeted main performance indicators (MPIs), or in Indonesian language called as IKU (*Indikator Kinerja Utama*), as decided by the Indonesian MoEC. The list of the main performance indicators (MPIs) was announced in the Decree of MoEC No. 3/M/2021, which also served as an amendment and dismissal of the previous MoEC Decree No. 754/P/2020. The latest eight main performance indicators (MPIs) include the following: (1) Graduate employability, (2) Students' extra-campus activity semester, (3) Faculty members' extra-campus activities, (4) Faculty members' qualification, (5) Research outputs, (6) Study program partnership, (7) Teaching and learning methodology, and (8) International accreditations.

The annual funding aid allotments granted to a state university are to be determined based on the previous year's level of achievement of the main performance indicators. The funding is provided through incentives sourced from State University Operational Assistance (BOPTN) and PTN-BH Funding Assistance (BPPTN-BH). The three funding mechanisms implemented are (1) performance contract-based funding between the MoEC and a public university, (2) a matching fund for the additional income that a public university has generated, and (3) a competitive fund or funds for aspiration projects that a public university has planned. The incentives are divided into two schemes, depending on a university's overall scores in all eight MPIs and a university's achievement of a single indicator of MPIs. Under this 2021 funding scheme policy, universities whose overall achievement of the MPIs is within the top 10% receive the largest proportion of incentives. In addition, universities with the highest score in each indicator of the eight MPIs are eligible for an additional bonus award. The details of the funding allocations of the 17 PTN-BHs, here based on the documents of each university's

2021 Performance Contract signed by the rector and DGHERT (Note: the documents are available upon a request forwarded to the authors).

Influence of the Top-Organizational Leadership Structure (Vice-Rectors)

According to Indonesian Government Regulation No. 16 Year 1999 regarding the establishment of PTN-BH, the highest leadership of Indonesian HEIs comprises a rector who is assisted by vice-rectors. At least two vice-rectors must be appointed to help manage institutional academic and nonacademic affairs, and additional vice-rectors—up to five—can be appointed according to the needs of the university and rector. In the Indonesian context, smaller HEIs are usually led by a rector and assisted by three vice-rectors; however, the bigger institutions are commonly regulated by a rector who is assisted by four vice-rectors. Although regulating the accepted number of vice-rectors, the Indonesian government permits universities to determine the fields of affairs managed by each vice-rector. Therefore, as shown in Table 5, three PTN-BHs appoint five vice-rectors, while most PTN-BHs have four vice-rectors.

Table 5 also provides interesting facts on the differences in the affairs divisions distributed to the vice-rectors of PTN-BHs that belong to the same batch and their position on the list. Among the first group of PTN-BHs, while three universities, U4, U3, and U1, are listed in the top three in the table, each assigns a vice-rector for research affairs, only one university, U2, does not have a vice-rector for research affairs. Filed in the sixth position, does not have a vice-rector dedicated to research affairs. It is surpassed by U7 and U11, which have a vice-rector responsible for academic affairs within the university's top-leader management. This pattern is also noticeable in U5 and U17, which are in the fourteenth and fifteenth positions. Although U5 and U17 assign one of their vice rectors to manage research affairs, these universities also assign more than two other sectors to manage by the same vice-rector. This contrasts with most other PTN-BHs, which typically assign one or two additional sectors to their vice-rectors in charge of research affairs. Lastly, U13 and U16, which are in the last two positions on the list, do not enlist research as one of the sectors managed by any one of their vice-rectors.

Table 3. Top Leadership Assisting the Rector of PTN-BH Universities

Cod es	Vice-Rector 1	Vice-Rector 2	Vice-Rector 3	Vice-Rector 4	Vice-Rector 5
U1	Academic and Student Affairs	Finance and Logistics	Research and Innovation	Human Resources and Assets	NA
U2	Education, Learning, and Student Affairs	Planning, Finance, and Information System	Research and Community Service	Human Resources and Assets	Cooperation and Alumni
U3	Academic and Student	Resources	Finance, Planning, and Development	Research and Innovation	NA
U4	Research , Innovation, and Community Development	Resources	Academic, Studentship, and Alumni	Internationalization, Digitalization, and Information	NA
U5	Academic and Student	Planning, Finance, and Infrastructure	Human Resources, Organization, and Information	Research , Innovation, Cooperation, and Alumni	NA

			System Technology		
U6	Education and Student	Resources, planning, and Finance	International Affairs, Collaboration, and Alumni Relations	Innovation and Business	NA
U7	Academic	Finance and Resources	Student, Alumni, and Student Entrepreneurship	Planning, Cooperation, and Internationalization	Research and Innovation
U8	Academic	Planning, Finance, and Infrastructure Resources	Students and Alumni	Research, Innovation, and Partnership	NA
U9	Academic and Student Affairs	Human Resources and Finance	Communication and Business	Research and innovation	NA
U10	Academics, Students, and Alumni	General and Human Resources	Research, Community Service, and Partnership	Information, Planning, and Development	Assets and Business Management
U11	Academics and Students	Resources and Finance	Innovation and Research	Planning, Partnership, Business, and Information	NA
U12	Academics and Student Affairs	Public Administration and Finance	Research and Innovation	Planning and Organization	NA
U13	Education and Student Affairs:	Finance and Resources	Planning, Organization, and Information System	Student and Alumni	NA
U14	Education, Teaching, Research , Community Service, and Innovation	Human Resources, Finance, and Assets	Student and Alumni	Planning, Partnership, and Public Relations	NA
U15	Academics	Public Administration and Resources	Student Affairs	Research, International Affairs, Partnership, and Business	NA
U16	Academics	Planning, Finance, Personnel Affairs	Student and Alumni	Planning, Development, and Partnership	NA
U17	Academics	Planning, Finance, Personnel Affairs	Student and Alumni	Partnership and Information	NA

Source: Respective universities websites accessed in March 2022

Discussion

The results of this study have highlighted that one of the primary goals of shaping national policies governing Indonesian PTN-BH universities is to support and enhance universities'

research performance. The objective is aimed at improving Indonesian higher education institutions' international reputation and global competitiveness as indicated by their position in various world university ranking systems, which is often evaluated through their rankings in various global university ranking systems that heavily weigh research performance. From the initiation of the policy related to PTN-BH in 1999 to 2020, the Indonesian government has continuously issued either new or amended versions of decrees and government regulations overseeing the establishment and the management of PTN-BH that somehow has affected the expected results as indicated in diverse performances of the existing PTN-BH universities.

The current study's findings show that it has been customary for policymakers to review and amend the regulations to improve the feasibility of the expected results; however, comprehensive evaluation and assessment need to be carefully assigned so that these revised regulations have the intended results. For instance, regarding the Indonesian PTN-BH policies, altering the requirements for universities to attain PTN-BH status has had dual effects. On the one hand, the policy encourages more universities to be included in the PTN-BH system. On the other hand, the quality or the performance of the applicant universities is not maintained to match the previously inaugurated PTN-BHs. Based on the findings, the regulation on the initiatives to upgrade the status of a public university into a PTN-BH has been found to affect the PTN-BHs' performance, either positively or negatively, particularly among those following the bottom-up procedure. The PTN-BH aspiring universities must fulfil the standard criteria before preparing their application proposal documents, leading to universities' efforts to improve the required aspects to be reported. However, the self-prepared assessment document is subject to inaccuracies and subjectivities, potentially making the applicants overestimate their initial readiness. Furthermore, the universities' capacity to adhere to the funding policy, which encompasses generating income, matching funds, and performance-based financing, directly impacts the allocation of their budgets, particularly regarding research activities.

Finally, the degree of autonomy granted to universities in determining their top-level management structure, including the appointment of a vice-rector responsible for overseeing research matters, significantly influences the research performance of these institutions. In the HEI context, university leaders are responsible for developing, implementing, and reviewing institutional or organizational policy (Cardno, 2018) while, at the same time, ensuring the institutional policy's compatibility with national policies and regulations. Furthermore, in line with Díaz-Fernández et al. (2020) and (Aboramadan, 2021), who have found the top management team composition's contribution to organizational performance, the structure and arrangement of the top management team under the rector that consists of the vice-rectors must be thoroughly reviewed and carefully decided.

CONCLUSION

The findings of our recent study have substantiated the significant impact of both national and institutional policies on the research performance of 17 Indonesian PTN-BH universities. Beyond national policies, institutional policies within a university are equally pivotal in shaping its performance. While this current study focused on assessing policy effects on universities' research performance, a follow-up study may be expanded to examine their impacts on universities' overall performance. More comprehensive future research could extend its scope to evaluate their influence on overall university performance. Future research of a more comprehensive nature might explore universities' strategic alignment with government regulations regarding PTN-BH to attain the highest level of autonomy and optimize results.

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